

Abstract: Evidence from psychology and neuroscience indicates that our spatial experience, including the bodily one, involves the integration of different sensory inputs within two different reference frames *egocentric* (body as reference of first-person experience) and *allocentric* (body as object in the physical world). Even if functional relations between these two frames are usually limited, they influence each other during the interaction between long- and short-term memory processes in spatial cognition. If, for some reasons, this process is impaired, the egocentric sensory inputs are no more able to update the contents of the allocentric representation of the body: the subject is locked to it. In our perspective, subjects with eating disorders are locked to an allocentric representation of their body, stored in long-term memory. A significant role in the locking may be played by the medial temporal lobe, and in particular by the connection between the hippocampal complex and amygdala.

Address correspondence to:

Prof. Giuseppe Riva,
Istituto Auxologico Italiano
Via Pelizza Da Volpedo 41
20149 Milan, Italy
E-mail: auxo.psylab[at]auxologico.it

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Nybrogatan 66, 114 41 Stockholm
Phone: 08-20 72 14 Plusgiro: 90 00 87 - 8
info@abkontakt.se
www.abkontakt.se

Neuroscience and Eating Disorders: The role of the medial-temporal lobe

Giuseppe Riva, Ph.D.

Evidence from psychology and neuroscience indicates that our spatial experience, including the bodily one, involves the integration of different sensory inputs within two different reference frames (1, 2): **egocentric** (body as reference of first-person experience) having its primary source in somatoperceptions - representations of the present state of the body and tactile stimuli from sensory inputs; **allocentric** (body as object in the physical world) having its primary source in somatorepresentations - abstract knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes related to body as an object of third-person experience.

These frames influence the way memories are stored and retrieved (3, 4): the rememberer may “see” the event from his or

her perspective as in normal perception (field mode), or “see” the self engaged in the event as an observer would (observer mode).

More, they influence the ability of representing and recalling our body: an egocentric representation of how our body looks is matched by an allocentric one, used by our brain in different situations (3, 5): from spatial cognition to social perception.

The functional relations between these two frames are usually limited (2). This is because the egocentric frame is based on an integrated, on-line percept of the current state of the body, while the allocentric one involves knowledge about one's body as a unique, continuous object.

However, Byrne and

colleagues (6) recently proposed a model that uses the interaction between egocentric and allocentric representations to account for the interaction between long- and short-term memory processes in spatial cognition. Specifically, long-term spatial memory involves the generation of allocentric representations in the hippocampus and surrounding medial temporal lobe structures. Instead, short-term spatial memory and imagery are modeled as egocentric representations of locations in the precuneus, driven either by perception or by long-term memory. Within this framework, the process of spatial encoding and retrieval requires a translation between the allocentric long-term memory and the egocentric spatial

updating, which occurs via a coordinate transformation in the posterior parietal and retrosplenial cortices.

On one side, an allocentric representation of the body - cued by knowledge of position and orientation and retrieved from long-term memory - is translated by the Papez's circuit in an egocentric representation that can influence the existing ones, including body dimensions and motor patterns (7).

On the other side, an egocentric representation of the body can influence an allocentric memory through the reactivation of a population of boundary vector cells located within parahippocampal cortex. If, for some reasons, this process is impaired, the egocentric sensory inputs are no more able to update the contents of the allocentric representation of the body: the subject is locked to it.

This is what apparently happens in eating disorders (ED): *a negative allocentric representation - that is not updated by contrasting egocentric parietal representations driven by perception (8) - primes the processing of any further body-related experience (9).*

Apparently, a significant role in the locking may be played by the medial temporal lobe, and in

particular by the connection between the hippocampal complex and amygdala. As we have seen, the hippocampus has a critical role in spatial memory by generating allocentric representations for long-term memory (6). Further, a recent neurological study showed an important role for the left hippocampus and some parahippocampal regions, in particular the entorhinal cortex, in episodic memory consolidation and recall (10).

These data suggest that the hippocampus may provide the spatial context appropriate to recollection of episodic events, explaining its role in the context-dependent fear conditioning found in ED. In fact, there is a strict link between hippocampus and amygdala (11): the hippocampal complex, by forming episodic representations of the emotional significance of a stimulus can lead to the activation of the amygdala, explaining the avoidance and negative feelings related to the body. At the same time, the amygdala may modulate both the storage and the consolidation of hippocampal-dependent memories, explaining the difficulty in updating the allocentric representation of the body.

Specifically, amygdala may modulate within-object binding in the perirhinal cortex enhancing

Figure 1
The etiology of eating disorders: from teasing to eating disorders

long-term consolidation of emotionally arousing objects (12): whatever is considered to be an integral component of the emotionally arousing object will also show enhanced long-term consolidation. For example, experiencing a tight pair of trousers may consolidate the allocentric representation of the body.

A growing body of evidence has demonstrated that stress, and in particular chronic stress, can cause hippocampal damage (13). Specifically, chronic stress produces consistent and reversible changes within the dendritic arbors of CA3 hippocampal neurons (13, 14). This process disrupts hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis activity, leading to dysregulated glucocorticoid release that, combined with hippocampal CA3 dendritic retraction, contributes to impaired spatial memory (14). Interestingly, some authors suggested that the onset of ED is often related to critical life events (personal and/or familiar) and that chronic stress is associated with the persistence of these disorders (15, 16). More, the ghrelin hormone, which increases during fasting, has been shown to defend against depressive-like symptoms of chronic stress (17).

Different neuroimaging data showed some impairment in the medial temporal lobe of ED patients. Connan and colleagues (18) found in anorectic patients a significant reduction in hippocampal volume (-8.2% right; -7.5% left) compared with healthy subjects. Wagner and colleagues (19) confronted female anorectic patients and healthy controls with their own digitally distorted body images: anorectics experienced a hyperresponsiveness in the parietal lobe, suggestive of a disturbance in the visuospatial processing of the own body shape. Yonezawa and colleagues (20) found bilateral decreased perfusion of the subcallosal gyrus, midbrain and posterior cingulate gyrus in both restricting and binge eating/purging anorectic patients, as compared with the controls. The abnormalities of regional cerebral blood flow disappear after recovery in both anorexia and bulimia nervosa (21).

The passage from a locked allocentric representation to an ED may be explained by social influence (Figure 1): media and culture promote diet as the best ways to improve body image satisfaction. However, the impossibility of updating the allocentric representation of the body, even after a demanding diet, locks the patient into an unsatisfying body.

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